

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF EDUCATING STUDENTS IN A PATRIOTIC SPIRIT THROUGH EXAMPLES OF UZBEKISTAN FOLK FOLK LITERATURE

Kadirkulov Nodirbek Hamrokul oglu

Independent researcher at the National Institute
of Educational Pedagogy named after Qori Niyoz

e-mail: qodirqulovnodirbek@380gmail.com tel:+998994429044

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20523397>

Аннотация: Мазкур мақолада ўқувчиларни ўзбек халқ оғзаки ижоди намуналари воситасида ватанпарварлик руҳида тарбиялашнинг педагогик шарт-шароитлари илмий-назарий ва амалий жиҳатдан таҳлил қилинади. Унда халқ оғзаки ижодининг тарбиявий имкониятлари, хусусан, дostonлар, эртақлар, мақол ва ривоятларнинг ўқувчиларда миллий ғурур, Ватанга садоқат, тарихий онг ва фуқаролик масъулиятини шакллантиришдаги ўрни ёритилади.

Калит сўзлар: Ватанпарварлик, халқ оғзаки ижоди, тарбия, педагогик шарт-шароитлар, миллий ғурур, тарбия, дostonлар, эртақлар, мақоллар, ўқувчилар.

Abstract: This article analyzes the pedagogical conditions for educating students in the spirit of patriotism through examples of Uzbek folk oral literature from a scientific, theoretical and practical perspective. It highlights the educational potential of folk oral literature, in particular, the role of epics, fairy tales, proverbs and legends in forming national pride, loyalty to the Motherland, historical awareness and civic responsibility in students.

Key words: Patriotism, folklore, education, pedagogical conditions, national pride, education, epics, tales, proverbs, students.

In today's globalization environment, educating the younger generation in the spirit of national values, forming in them loyalty to the Motherland, national pride and civic responsibility is one of the urgent pedagogical problems. In particular, the effective use of examples of Uzbek folk oral creativity is of great importance in developing patriotic feelings in students. Because folk oral creativity is an invaluable resource that has been formed over the centuries and embodies the historical memory, spiritual heritage and life experience of the people. It is known that independent Uzbekistan is the homeland of great scholars and thinkers, one of the cradles of world civilization, an integral part of the world's tangible and intangible heritage, a hotbed of spirituality and enlightenment, a country with high intellectual potential. Turning to history to instill such a great heritage in the hearts of the growing generation can be very effective, because it is history that is the source of understanding national identity, finding one's own identity. A people who have not mastered the historical experience of the development of their national culture and spirituality are not capable of national growth and development, therefore, the stronger the patriotism and sense of homeland in young people, the stronger and more stable their need for spiritual development will be, patriotic education is an important factor in strengthening the spiritual foundations of independence. That is why the goal of educational and educational activities carried out in our country is aimed at forming a patriotic person who is capable of showing examples of selflessness for the development of the country. The following pedagogical conditions are of great importance in the formation of patriotic feelings in students:

Firstly, it is necessary to systematically and purposefully use examples of folk oral creativity in the educational process. In this process, the teacher must select materials appropriate to the topic and combine them with the content of the lesson.

Secondly, the use of interactive methods increases efficiency. For example, through methods such as role-playing games, staging, debate, and "mental attack", students are actively engaged and they gain a deeper understanding of the content of folk oral creativity.

Thirdly, it is important to take into account the age and individual characteristics of students. If it is more appropriate to use fairy tales and riddles in primary grades, then in higher grades it is effective to pay attention to epics and historical narratives.

Fourthly, it is necessary to ensure the coherence of education and upbringing. That is, the knowledge gained during the lesson should be reinforced through extracurricular activities, spiritual and educational meetings, and literary evenings.

Fifthly, it is important to create an environment that fosters respect and interest in national values. In this regard, the cooperation of school, family, and community plays a special role.

Also, the teacher's pedagogical skills, creativity, and devotion to national values are important factors in educating through folk oral creativity. Because the teacher has a positive impact on students not only as a teacher, but also as an educator.

Each method and form of patriotic education forms its own educational aspects in young students. For example, lessons on courage form a positive thought for a student who is just being formed, who is looking for his ideal in life, that he should be like this person, while sports competitions form such qualities as teamwork, caring for his comrades, caring for the team, fighting for the honor of the team and himself. During the trips, students will receive detailed information about the courage of their ancestors, their glorious deeds. In addition, regular organization of events such as public reading of patriotic literature and books with students and theoretical conferences and discussions based on these books - on the one hand, it fosters a desire for reading books among young people, and on the other hand, through these books, it fosters the national beliefs of our people, spiritual values, duty, love for the homeland, the future of the nation, putting the interests of the country above personal interests, and increases artistic literacy.

Due to the large audience and impact of patriotic films and videos regularly broadcast through the mass media, it allows achieving high results in a short time. This can also be observed in the examples of a number of foreign and Commonwealth countries. For example, we can learn from the media that in recent years, state-owned television channels of the Russian Federation have been widely presenting videos and feature films on military-patriotic topics, and this has ensured the rapid growth of the spirit of patriotism among young people. In our country, increasing the number and quality of films on patriotic topics will also have a positive effect. By organizing more and more systematic screenings of films on central and private television channels, we will have the opportunity to partially limit various shows and films on everyday topics that promote light-hearted and "mass culture". Thus, young students

№	Criteria	explanation
1	Love for the Motherland	

2.	Patriotism (deep understanding of the history of the Motherland)	
3	Dedication	
4	Duty	
5	Responsibility	
6	Heroism	
7	Patience	
8	Loyalty	
9	Honesty	
10	Pride	

As a result of scientific analysis, we consider it appropriate to interpret the content of these criteria as follows.

Love of the country: it is a high human feeling to love the country, family and neighborhood where one was born and grew up, to honor it, to protect it and to be selfless for its prosperity. This feeling is inherent in human nature and is a part of faith.

Patriotism: showing respect for the country's history and values, contributing to its development.

Selflessness. An important moral criterion of patriotism in students is loyalty to one's country, people, chosen path, profession, idea, and devotion to it. Self-sacrifice requires a person to have a big heart, zeal, and most importantly, a strong belief in oneself and one's own strength. In addition, self-sacrifice is one of the highest virtues inherent in a person, and a self-sacrificing person is ready to sacrifice his legitimate interests, sometimes even his life, for the benefit of others, and does so when necessary.

Duty. This concept is indirectly important in the quality of patriotism formed in youth. Lack of sense of duty, irresponsibility is a sign of an indifferent, indifferent approach to the interests of the homeland, people, and future problems.

Responsibility. Responsibility is a spiritual factor aimed at understanding duty and acting on it. Responsibility implies personal responsibility for the fulfillment of tasks of social and spiritual significance, for the implementation of the moral principles underlying the actions and actions.

Heroism. To be selfless every day, every hour, to tirelessly and tirelessly mobilize oneself towards great goals drop by drop, particle by particle, to make this virtue a constant, daily criterion of activity - this is true heroism.

Endurance. Not only to endure any difficulties, but also to overcome them with perseverance in the interests of the Motherland.

Loyalty. This virtue is manifested through loyalty to the Motherland, duty, and appreciation of solidarity, unity and friendship. In the development of society, educating young people in the spirit of loyalty to the country is one of the most important tasks today.

Pride. This virtue becomes reality through the feeling of being proud of the success, honor, achievements, and values of the people and nation. This feeling is manifested in the following forms: being proud of the achievements, reputation, and dignity of the nation, not being indifferent to its problems; being devoted to one's country and nation; preserving the

material and spiritual heritage of one's nation; respecting the customs, traditions, and values of the people, enriching and improving them; expressing love for one's nation in practical activities.

Honesty. This is refraining from doing something, thing, word, or action that is inappropriate or unacceptable to oneself, feeling embarrassed, ashamed; defending one's self-respect, not giving up one's reputation [99;82-84]. The fact that these qualities are formed in today's youth indicates the presence of a sense of patriotism in them. "In all spheres and sectors of our life, millions of our youth serve with loyalty and selflessness, fulfilling such an honorable duty as the defense of the Motherland" [25;440].

Patriotic qualities in students are formed and developed on the basis of the interconnectedness and continuity of the above-mentioned criteria. Therefore, one of the urgent tasks is to develop a methodology for the strong formation of such moral qualities in the educational process.

In conclusion, the use of examples of Uzbek folk oral creativity is an effective pedagogical tool in the formation of patriotic feelings in students. By properly organizing this process, didactically and methodically justifying it, it is possible to educate the young generation as a person who is loyal to the Motherland, has national pride, and is well-rounded. Therefore, the wide and purposeful use of examples of folklore in the educational process is one of the important tasks of today.

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар:

1. Мирзиёев Сх.М. Еркин ва фаровон, демократик О'збекистон давлатини биргаликда барпо етамиз. – Тосҳкент: О'збекистон, 2017.
2. О'збек халқ оғзаки ижоди. Достонлар то'плами. – Тосҳкент: Фафур Ғулом номидаги насҳриёт, 2015.
3. О'збек халқ ертаклари. – Тосҳкент: Сҳарқ насҳриёти, 2018.
4. Маҳмудов Н., Нурмонов А. Она тили ва адабиёт таълими методикаси. – Тосҳкент: О'қитувчи, 2017.
5. Ёлдошқев Ж., Усмонов С. Педагогика асослари. – Тосҳкент: О'қитувчи, 2012.
6. Тўхтаходжаев Н. Педагогика назарияси ва тарихи. – Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 2010.
7. Қодиров Б. Тарбия назарияси. – Тошкент: Фан, 2016. •
8. Ўзбекистон Республикаси "Таълим тўғрисида"ги Қонуни. – Тошкент, 2020..